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CONVERSATION ANALYSIS OF REPAIR IN A TALK SHOW ‘HITAM PUTIH – SISI LAIN ANTASARI AZHAR’

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ABSTRACT

Transcription represents spoken language in any interaction and communication that be recorded from an audio tool or a video tool which later be transcribed into written language for conversation analysis. In this study, the source of the transcription regarding conversation Analysis is from a talk show entitled “Hitam Putih – Sisi Lain Antasari Azhar” between 2 famous people. They are Antasari Azhar, Indonesian ex-chief of Corruption Eradication Commission, and Deddy Corbuzier, a well-known talk show host. This is a qualitative descriptive study. The aim of the study is to analyse the interaction in a form of transcribed conversation using Conversation Analysis (CA) approach, especially “repair”. The findings reveal that throughout the conversation, repair processes are frequently happened to correct misunderstanding and mispronouncing utterances that are often occurred in a conversation.

Keywords: Conversation Analysis, language, repair, transcription

INTRODUCTION: INTRODUCTION

Conversation Analysis (CA) is a research approach within the field of sociology and linguistics that aims to understand the structure and organization of human interaction through the detailed examination of a written recorded conversations through what is called as transcription. Since the basic data for conversation analysis is naturally occurring talk, and if such talk is used for detailed analysis, it must first be recorded and then transcribed.(1) CA also emphasizes the study of how people produce and interpret conversational turns in real-time. It looks at the sequential flow of conversation, turn-taking, repair mechanisms (how misunderstandings are resolved), and other aspects of interactional dynamics.

Researchers using CA employ various analytical techniques to examine conversational data, including transcription conventions that capture pauses, overlaps, intonation, and gestures. They often use tools like conversation transcripts, sequential analysis, and discourse analysis to uncover patterns and structures in interaction. All in all, conversation analysis provides a rigorous framework for understanding how people communicate, negotiate meanings, and manage social relationships through everyday conversation. It offers insights into the underlying norms and practices that shape social interaction and communication patterns.

Therefore, knowing that Conversation Analysis can be a powerful tool to unveil certain patterns in communication, which in this case a repair, this study will utilize CA in a natural conversation which is the source of the primary data collected through a talk show entitled ‘Hitam Putih – Sisi Lain Antasari Azhar’ between 2 famous people. They are Antasari Azhar, Indonesian ex-chief of the Corruption Eradication Commission, and Deddy Corbuzier, a well-known talk show host.

Overall, the interaction between these two and the repair processes that occur during the conversation are the features that will be discussed further in this study.

There have been several studies regarding CA, in which they are: Conversation Analysis of Repair in EFL Classroom by Handayani L, R., Dollah, S., & Jabu, B. (2021); A Conversation Analysis of Repair Strategies in Indonesian Elementary EFL Students by Novitasari, T., & Imperiani, E. D. (2020), and; A Conversation Analysis of Repair in Classroom Interaction by Pujarwanti, C. A. (2019). Their study discover that repairs were indeed occurred during the interaction between teacher and students.

However, since their studies were too focused on spoken interaction in English, the conversation tend to be rigid and unnatural for a reason that students cannot fully express their talk. This gives rise a question whether students were able to initiate repair strategy, or they simply did not know how to talk in English, or even if they did, they only had a little understanding of English at best. Based on that case, this study will examine further into a domain where a natural conversation does occur, so that the end-result could show that the repair occurrence between speaker and interlocutor are performed because they know what must be repaired throughout the conversation.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study is a qualitative descriptive that uses Conversation Analysis (CA) as an approach to analyze several aspects in communication, including: turn-taking; adjacency pairs; and repair to comprehend how individuals interpret social interactions. Based on the aforementioned CA transcription method, the focus in this study will be in repair since that aspect of the interaction revealed to be more interesting within the data. As a note, the transcription of selected conversation that are used as the primary data in this study is the excerpts from the conversation between 2 people in a talk show called ‘Hitam Putih’. Additionally, only the excerpts containing aspects of repair are taken as repair is the main focus of this study. Schegloff, Jefferson & Sacks (1977, p.364) noted that the one who performs a repair is not necessarily the one who initiated the repair operation. In fact, both self-repair and other-repair sometimes could be transpired from exclusive types of repair initiation from either self-initiation of repair by the speaker of the trouble source and other-initiation of repair by any party other than speaker of the trouble source.(5)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This study analyses repairs into 4 categories that can be found in this conversation analysis. For instance, the transcribed text of an interview from ‘Hitam Putih – Sisi Lain Antasari Azhar’ between Antasari Azhar, referred as Speaker A, and Deddy Corbuzier, referred as Speaker D. The analysis are divided into 4 repair processes that are shown in the following excerpts.

1. Self-repair from other-initiation

D: kegiatan(.)anda itu ngapain pa:k?

activity-you-it-what-sir

what kind of activity(.)that you had done((in prison))si:r?

(0.4)

A: ya kegiatan warga binaan la:h

activity-inmate

yeah certain inmate activities indee:d

(0.2)

D: ke:giatan warna binaa:n?

activity-Inmate

in:mate activite:s?

A: iyah(.)jadi ibadah(.)olahraga...

yeah-so-worship-exercise

yeah(.)such as worshipping(.)exercising...

Conversations above points that speaker D is initially asking about what activity Speaker A has done while in the prison and be responded by saying he was doing some inmate activities. This utterance ‘inmate activities’ might be the trouble source since the Speaker D does not get the clear idea about what kind of inmate activity the Speaker A does. Accordingly, Speaker D restates the utterance “inmate activities?” in hope that Speaker A will make it clearer which is then be self-repaired by saying ‘yeah’ with extended explanation that his inmate activities such as worshipping, exercising, etc.

2. Self-repair from self-initiation

A: <saya diangkat menjadi koordinator pemuka:>

I-promoted-become-coordinator-leader

<I was promoted as a coordinator leader:>

D: koordinatOR?

koordinatOR?

A: pemuka

leader

D: pemuka:?

leader?

A: nah pemuka itu::(.)apa jaman dulu ya? foreman itu ya?

leader-this-what-past-foreman-that

this leader thing::(.)what we used to call in the past again? foreman right?

D: hm-hm

As can be noticed, a lot of repetitions happened when the Speaker A firstly says he was promoted as a coordinator leader which seems to be an unfamiliar word. Because Speaker D later interrupts and repeats word by word by asking ‘‘coordinator?’’ which is responded as ‘‘leader’’ by the Speaker A, and then re-asking ‘‘leader?’’ in which again Speaker A clarifies that (coordinator) leader is what we used to call ‘‘foreman’’ in the first place. This result indicates that Speaker A who initiate the trouble source is finally try to self-repair. Hereafter, Speaker D who finally understands, yields the Speaker A to keep holding the floor by signalling a continuer ‘‘hm-hm’’.

3. Other-repair from other-initiation

D: bapak antasari mengatakan bahwa anda tidak stress

Mr.Antasari-say-that-you-not-stress

Mr. Antasari, you said that you did not stressed out

(0.2)

A: saya tidak stres(h)(0.2)saya tidak stress didalam situ kenapa:?

I-not-stress-I-not-stress-inside-that-why?

I did not ↓stress(h)(0.2)I did not stress there ((the prison)) why: ?

saya ikhlas menjalani

I-sincere-serve

because I sincerely served out

D: ikhlas menjalani hal [tersebut]

sincere-undergo-that-thing

you sincerely served those [inmate activities]

A: [menjalani iya:]

serve out-yes

[serve out yes:]

In above, Speaker D denotes that Speaker A does not stress out while in the prison which subsequently confirmed by Speaker A that he does not stress because he sincerely serves out the trial. Speaker D, believing what Speaker A has said is an incomplete utterance, immediately interrupts and repairs by restating Speaker A ‘‘sincerely serves out any inmate activity before’’. Speaker D interruption is regarded as other-repair because he makes clearer the trouble source utterance from Speaker A. Additionally, last response from speaker A indicates that he might wanted to self-repair his unfinished utterance as he seemingly began to resume his speaking but unfortunately Speaker D is faster to self-select and take the

turn. Besides, at the end of the Speaker D second turn and the beginning of the Speaker A last turn, there is an overlapping which can be assumed as the Speaker A's continuation effort that being overwritten by Speaker D's interruption that resulting on an overlap.

4. Other-repair from self-initiation

A: suda:h(.)hari pertama juga beliau udah kontak saya(.)ucapin selamat saya baik-baik(.)satu- satunya

already-day-first-also-he-already-contact-me-utter-compliment-only-one

sure:ly(.)he((Mr. JK))already contacted me since day one(.)uttering a compliment(.) the only one(.)

D: satu-satunya yang mengucapkan selamat

only-one-who-congratulate

the only one who congratulates

A: iya(.)Pak JK

yes(.)Mr. JK

This circumstance describes Speaker A who currently holds the floor, made an unclear utterance by saying "the only one" before yield the floor. This is quite ambiguous since what "the only one" he refers to? which is spontaneously responded by Speaker D by explicitly saying that "the only one who congratulates". This is the other-repair because Speaker D is not the one who triggers the trouble source who comes up with ambiguous words. Thereafter, Speaker A accepts the repair and admits by saying yes, that the one who congratulates is Mr. JK.

Furthermore, repair could be distinguished based on its initiation place. Self-initiated repairs have their initiations placed in three main types of positions. The first may be placed within the same turn as their trouble source, the second may be placed in the turn's transition space, and the third may be placed in third turn to the trouble-source turn.(5) First example is as follows:

A: ternyata(.)anak saya(0.2)tidak mau itu dimut- dimunculkan

obviously-my-child-not-want-that-showed

obviously(.)my daughter(0.2)does not want that to be sho- showed

Obviously, example above shows that the partial word following by a 'hyphen' that is repaired right after them are the repaired words in which occurred in the same turn. While second example is as follows:

A: saya bilang saya minta ijin bahwa(.)untuk kali ini saya minta saya putar sendiri

I-say-I-ask-permission-that-for-this-time-I-ask-I-play-myself

I said that I asked a permission for(.)this time that I want to play it by myself

(0.2)

→ **aa- apa? tivi yang menyiarkan(.)resepsi anak saya**

what-TV-that-broadcast-marriage-my child

aa- what? TV that broadcasts(.)my daughter's marriage

Excerpt above explains that the next line where self-repair happened is potentially allowing a turn's transition space. The transition space, roughly, is the environment of a turn's possible completion, at which possible transition to a next speaker becomes relevant (Sacks et al.,1974). Lastly, the third example is as follows:

A: Pak JK da:tang(.)bawa kue:

Mr.JK-come-bring-cake

Mr. JK came, by bringing a cake

D: bawa kuEH?

bring-cake

bringing a cake?

A: bawa kue titipan(.)Ibu JK

bring-cake-entrusted-Mrs.JK

bringing a cake from(.)Mrs. JK

Condition above attests that third turn repair is just the same as what Schegloff (1997) said "...the turn subsequent to that which follows the trouble-source turn ...". Clearly, last turn is expanded utterance "bringing a cake from Mrs. JK" as well as third turn repair which is preceded by trouble source "bringing a cake".(6)

CONCLUSION

The analysis concludes that with repair, someone can correct any misunderstanding and mispronouncing utterance that occurred within conversation analysis. Moreover, either self-repair or other-repair, this can be occurred depend on the initiation place and the trouble source, since the position determines which category of repair is initiated. By means of 'repair', it refers to practices for dealing with problems or troubles in speaking, hearing, and understanding the talk in conversation and in other forms of talk-in-interaction, for that matter. (6)

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